

**A catalogue of the genus *Callimetopus* Blanchard, 1853
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the world fauna**

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Abstract: The catalogue of the genus *Callimetopus* Blanchard, 1853 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the world fauna which based on the literature data and most important online databases is provided. It contains data on 41 species which are distributed in the Philippines, Indonesia and Malaysia. Each species is represented by synonyms, literature, most significant databases, and data on the distribution and depositories of the type material.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Callimetopus* Blanchard, 1853 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) belongs to the tribe Pteropliini of the subfamily Lamiinae. Members of this genus are distributed in the Oriental region and represented by forty one species. Thirty six species are known from the Philippines, six from Indonesia and two from Malaysia. For the Philippine archipelago the largest number of species are known from Luzon Island (twenty species) and from Mindanao Island (nine species); four species are known for Panay Island, three species for Samar Island, two species on each for Leyte, Negros and Sibuyan islands, and one species on each for Basilan, Dinagat, Mindoro, Palawan and Siargao islands. Two species from the Philippines have been described without exact indication of the type locality. In Indonesia three species of the genus are known from Moluccas archipelago, two species from Sulawesi (Celebes) Island and one species from Sumatra and Borneo Islands respectively. Two species are known from peninsular part of Malaysia. The distribution of several species is still insufficiently investigated and perhaps they are more widely distributed in the

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Oriental region.

Breuning (1962) published key for 25 species of the genus *Callimetopus*. The key included *C. principalis* Heller, 1924, *C. superbus* Breuning, 1947, *C. pulchellus* Schultze, 1922 and *C. gloriosus* Schultze, 1922, which were transferred later by Vives (2005) to the genus *Acronia* Westwood, 1863, and *C. multialboguttatus* Breuning, 1961, transferred to the genus *Faustabryna* Breuning, 1961. Dela Cruz & Adorada (2012) published determination key for 19 species (one - *nomen nudum*?) of the Philippine *Callimetopus* and described six new species from the Philippines: *C. acerdentibus* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 and *C. niveuseta* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 from Luzon Island, *C. stanleyi* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 from Mindanao Island, *C. mindorensis* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 from Mindoro Island, *C. cretumus* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 and *C. pectoralis* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012 from the Philippines without exact locality. Both keys does not contains data about all species of the genus. Several species are described by one or a few specimens and still known only on the type material. In addition, some of descriptions are short or with uncertain differential diagnoses which makes some difficulties to use these keys during species identification. After Breuning (1962), several new species of *Callimetopus* were described recently. The genital structures of species of *Callimetopus* were described and illustrated for the first time by dela Cruz and Adorada (2012).

In last year author published four articles (Barševskis 2015c, 2015d, 2015e, 2016 [in press]) on the genus *Callimetopus* and described seven new endemic species from the Philippine archipelago, five species of which are found on the Luzon Island, one on the Mindanao Island and one in Leyte, Luzon, Mindanao and Samar islands.

This study presents the catalogue of the genus *Callimetopus* of the world fauna. It is based on the published literature and the most important online databases. The catalogue contains data on the synonymy, references to the literature, data on the distribution and depositories. Used online databases downloaded to 03/08/2016.

ABBREVIATIONS

The following abbreviations of the museums or private collections are used in the present paper:

BPIM - Bureau of Plant Industry, Entomological Museum (Manila, Philippines)

BSMP - Bureau of Science (Manila, Philippines)

DUBC - Daugavpils University Beetles Collection (Ilgas, Latvia)

EVC - private collection of Eduard Vives (Terrassa, Spain)

IRSN - Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique

JRAC - private collection of J.R. Adorada (Laguna, Philippines)

MNHN - Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle (France, Paris)

MNHU - Museum fur Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universitat (Germany, Berlin)

MPMP - National Museum of the Philippines (Manila, Philippines)

NRS - Naturhistoriska riksmuseet (Sweden, Stockholm)

RNHL - Nationaal Natuurhistorische Museum ("Naturalis")

[formerly Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie] (Netherlands, Leiden)

UPPC - Museum of Natural History, University of the Philippines (Laguna, Philippines)

ZSMA - Zoologische Staatssammlung (Germany, Munchen)

CATALOGUE

Callimetopus Blanchard, 1853

1. *Callimetopus acerdentibus* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus acerdentibus: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 110, 106

Callimetopus acerdentibus: Barševskis, 2015a: 411

Callimetopus acerdentibus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: UPPC

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2. *Callimetopus albatus* (Newman, 1842)

Euclea albata: Newman, 1842: 290

Euclea albata: Lacordaire, 1872

Callimetopus albatus: Breuning, 1962: 453, 452

Callimetopus albata: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 103, 105

Callimetopus albatus: Barševskis, 2016 [in press]

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: BMNH

3. *Callimetopus anichtchenkoi* Barševskis, 2015

Callimetopus anichtchenkoi: Barševskis, 2015b: 1029

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: DUBC

4. *Callimetopus antonkozlovi* Barševskis, 2016

Callimetopus antonkozlovi: Barševskis, 2016 [in press.]

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org

Distribution: Philippines (Leyte, Luzon and Mindanao islands).

Type: DUBC

5. *Callimetopus bilineatus* Vives, 2015

Callimetopus bilineatus: Vives, 2015: 54

Callimetopus bilineatus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/ **Distribution:** Philippines (Mindanao
Island).

Type: EVC

6. *Callimetopus capito* (Pascoe, 1865)

Euclea capito: Pascoe, 1865: 149

Euclea mesoleuca: Pascoe, 1865: 150

Euclea mesoleuca: Schultze, 1920: 198

Callimetopus capito: Breuning, 1962: 453, 452

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Callimetopus capito m. *mesoleucus*: Breuning, 1962: 453

Callimetopus mesoleuca: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Callimetopus capito: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon and Sibuyan islands).

Types: BMNH

Callimetopus mesoleuca: BMNH (syntypes)

7. *Callimetopus cordifer* Heller, 1924

Niphonoclea rhombifera ab. *cordifera*: Heller, 1924: 202

Callimetopus cordifer: Breuning, 1962: 461

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Panay Island).

Type: SNSD

8. *Callimetopus cretumus* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus cretumus: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 106, 105

Callimetopus cretumus: Barševskis, 2015a: 411

Callimetopus cretumus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines.

Type: MPMP

9. *Callimetopus cynthia* (Thomson, 1865)

Euclea cynthia: Thomson, 1865: 549

Proteuclea sulphureomaculata: Schultze, 1916: 293

Euclea cynthia: Heller, 1926: 196

Callimetopus cynthia: Breuning, 1962: 457

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

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Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: MNHN

10. *Callimetopus cynthioides* Breuning, 1958

Callimetopus cynthioides: Breuning, 1958: 32

Callimetopus cynthioides: Breuning, 1962: 457

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: MNHN

11. *Callimetopus danilevskyi* Barševskis, 2015

Callimetopus danilevskyi: Barsevskis, 2015a: 412

Callimetopus danilevskyi: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027, 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: DUBC

12. *Callimetopus degeneratus* (Heller, 1924)

Euclea rhombifera degenerata: Heller, 1924: 203

Callimetopus degeneratus: Breuning, 1962: 461, 451

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Sibuyan Island).

Type: SNSD

13. *Callimetopus griseus* Breuning, 1960

Callimetopus griseus: Breuning, 1960: 4

Callimetopus griseus: Breuning, 1962: 459

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
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Distribution: Philippines (Panay Island).

Type: SNSD

14. *Callimetopus illecebrosus* (Pascoe, 1865)

Euclea illecebrosa: Pascoe, 1865: 150

Euclea casta: Thomson, 1865: 549

Callimetopus celebensis: Breuning, 1938: 41

Callimetopus illecebrosus: Breuning, 1962: 459

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sulawesi [Celebes] Island) and Malaysia (peninsular part).

Types: BMNH (syntypes)

Euclea casta: MNHN

Callimetopus celebensis: IRSN

15. *Callimetopus irroratus* (Newman, 1842)

Euclea irrorata: Newman, 1842: 290

Niphonoclea bifasciata: Fischer, 1934: 3

Callimetopus irroratus m. *albidus*: Breuning, 1947: 30

Callimetopus irroratus: Breuning, 1961: 235

Callimetopus irroratus m. *bifasciatus*: Breuning, 1962: 452

Callimetopus irroratus: Breuning, 1962: 452, 451

Callimetopus irroratus m. *albidus*: Breuning, 1962: 452

Callimetopus irrorata: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 106

Niphonoclea bifasciata: Lingafelter et al, 2014: 29

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Leyte, Luzon, Mindanao and Samar islands).

Types: BMNH (syntypes)

Callimetopus irroratus m. *albidus*: NRS

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16. *Callimetopus juliae* Barševskis, 2016

Callimetopus juliae: Barševskis, 2016 [in press]

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: DUBC

17. *Callimetopus latemaculatus* Breuning - *NOMEN NUDUM?*

Callimetopus latemaculatus: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Online databases: www.lamiinae.org

Distribution: Philippines.

18. *Callimetopus laterivitta* (Heller, 1915)

Proteuclea laterivitta: Heller, 1915: 245

Callimetopus laterivitta: Breuning, 1962: 457

Callimetopus laterivitta: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: SNSD

19. *Callimetopus lazarevi* Barsevskis, 2015

Callimetopus lazarevi: Barsevskis, 2015a: 414

Callimetopus lazarevi: Barsevskis, 2015c: 157

Callimetopus lazarevi: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027, 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Mindanao Island).

Type: DUBC

20. *Callimetopus lituratus* (Aurivillius, 1926)

Niphonoclea liturata: Aurivillius, 1926: 106

Callimetopus litturatus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

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Distribution: Indonesia (Moluccas: Buru Island).

Type: RNHL

21. *Callimetopus longicollis* (Schwarzer, 1931)

Niphonoclea longicollis: Schwarzer, 1931: 69

Callimetopus longicollis: Breuning, 1962: 454, 450

Callimetopus longicollis: Vives, 2005: 7

Callimetopus longicollis: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 104

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Dinagat and Luzon islands).

Type:

22. *Callimetopus longior* Hudepohl, 1990

Callimetopus longior: Hudepohl, 1990: 288

Callimetopus longior: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 104

Callimetopus longior: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon and Negros islands).

Type: ZSMA

23. *Callimetopus lumawigi* Breuning, 1980

Callimetopus lumawigi: Breuning, 1980: 165

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Mindanao Island).

Type: MNHN

24. *Callimetopus mindorensis* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus mindorensis dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 114, 104

Callimetopus mindorensis: Barševskis, 2015a: 411

Callimetopus mindorensis: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

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Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Mindoro Island).

Type: UPPC

25. *Callimetopus nigratarsis* (Pascoe, 1865)

Euclea nigratarsis: Pascoe, 1865: 150

Euclea bizonata: Thomson, 1865: 549

Euclea bizonata: Nonfried, 1894: 196

Callimetopus nigratarsis: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Callimetopus nigratarsis: Barševskis, 2015b: 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Indonesia (Sumatra, Moluccas: Amboin and Ceram islands), Malaysia (peninsular part).

Types: BMNH

Euclea bizonata: MNHN

26. *Callimetopus niveuseta* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus niveuseta: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 108, 105

Callimetopus niveuseta: Barševskis, 2015a: 411

Callimetopus niveuseta: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon island).

Type: UPPC

27. *Callimetopus ochreosignatus* Breuning, 1959

Callimetopus ochreosignatus: Breuning, 1959: 160

Callimetopus ochreosignatus: Breuning, 1962: 454

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
[https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w](https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o)
[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: MNHU

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28. *Callimetopus ornatus* (Schultze, 1934)

Niphonoclea ornata: Schultze, 1934: 313

Callimetopus ornatus: Breuning, 1961: 235

Callimetopus ornatus: Breuning, 1962: 450, 456

Callimetopus ornatus: Vives, 2011: 16

Callimetopus ornatus: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Callimetopus ornatus: Barsevskis, 2015a: 411, 415

Callimetopus ornatus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Samar Island). The distribution in Mindanao Island is need in confirmation.

Type: SNSD

29. *Callimetopus palawanus* Schultze, 1934

Proteuclea palawana: Schultze, 1934: 313

Callimetopus palawanus: Breuning, 1962: 458

Callimetopus palawanus: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Palawan Island).

Type: SNSD

30. *Callimetopus panayanus* (Schultze, 1920)

Euclea panayana: Schultze, 1920: 198

Callimetopus panayanus: Breuning, 1962: 455

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Panay Island).

Type: SNSD

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31. *Callimetopus pantherinus* Blanchard, 1853

Callimetopus pantherinus: Blanchard, 1853: 304

Callimetopus nodicornis: Ritsema, 1892: 38

Callimetopus pantherinus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w>

[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Indonesia (Moluccas).

Types: MNHN

Callimetopus nodicornis: RNHL

32. *Callimetopus paracasta* Breuning, 1965

Callimetopus paracasta: Breuning, 1965: 84

Callimetopus paracasta: Barševskis, 2015: 1027, 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w>

[=o, www.biolib.cz](http://www.biolib.cz)

Distribution: Indonesia, Malaysia (?) (Borneo island).

Type: MNHU

33. *Callimetopus pectoris* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus pectoris: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 105

Callimetopus pectoris: Barševskis, 2015b: 411

Callimetopus pectoralis: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines.

Type: BPIM

34. *Callimetopus rhombifer* (Heller, 1913)

Euclea rhombifera: Heller, 1913: 158

Callimetopus rhombifer: Breuning, 1962: 460

Callimetopus rhombiferus: Barševskis, 2015b: 1028

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,

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<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Indonesia (Celebes Island), Philippines (Panay Island).

Type: BSMP

35. *Callimetopus ruficollis* Heller, 1915

Euclea ruficollis: Heller, 1915: 244

Callimetopus ruficollis: Breuning, 1962: 456

Callimetopus ruficollis: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 104

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>,

www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: SNSD

36. *Callimetopus samarensis* Vives, 2012

Callimetopus samarensis: Vives, 2012: 43

Callimetopus samarensis: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>,

www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Samar Island).

Type: EVC

37. *Callimetopus shavrini* Barševskis, 2015

Callimetopus shavrini: Barševskis, 2015b: 1030

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: DUBC

37a. *Callimetopus siargoanus mindanaonis* Breuning, 1980

Callimetopus siargoanus mindanaonis: Breuning, 1980: 164

Callimetopus siargoanus mindanaonis: Hudepohl, 1983: 183

Callimetopus siargoanus mindanaonis: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/,

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<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Mindanao Island).

Type: MNHN

37b. *Callimetopus siargoanus siargoanus* (Schultze, 1919)

Euclea siargoana Schultze, 1919: 547

Callimetopus siargoanus: Breuning, 1961: 235

Callimetopus siargoanus; Breuning, 1962: 463

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>,

www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Siargao Island).

Type: SNSD

38. *Callimetopus stanleyi* dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012

Callimetopus stanleyi: dela Cruz & Adorada, Philippine Ent., 2012, 26(2): 116, 104

Callimetopus stanleyi: Barševskis, 2015a: 411

Callimetopus stanleyi: Barševskis, 2015b: 1027

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Mindanao Island).

Type: JRAC

39. *Callimetopus tagalus* (Heller, 1899)

Euclea tagala: Heller, 1899: 6

Euclea tagala rufofasciata: Schultze, 1919: 547

Euclea tagala: Schultze, 1919: 547

Euclea tagala var. *tricolor*: Heller, 1921: 540

Callimetopus tagalus: Breuning, 1962: 462, 451

Callimetopus tagalus m. *tricolor*: Breuning, 1962: 463

Callimetopus tagalus m. *rufofasciatus*: Breuning, 1962: 463

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,

lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/,

www.catalogueoflife.org,

<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>,

www.biolib.cz

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Distribution: Philippines (Basilan and Mindanao islands).

Types: SNSD

Euclea tagala rufofasciata: SNSD

Euclea tagala var. *tricolor*: SNSD

40. *Callimetopus variolosus* (Schultze, 1920)

Euclea variolosa: Schultze, 1920: 198

Callimetopus variolosus: Breuning, 1962: 454, 451

Callimetopus variolosa: dela Cruz & Adorada, 2012: 104

Callimetopus variolosus: Barševskis, 2016 [in press]

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
lully.snv.jussieu.fr/titan/, www.catalogueoflife.org,
<https://apps2.cdfa.ca.gov/publicApps/plant/bycidDB/wdefault.asp?w=o>, www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon, Negros and Mindanao islands).

Type: SNSD

41. *Callimetopus zhantievi* Barševskis, 2015

Callimetopus zhantievi Barševskis, 2015c: 156

Online databases: www.cerambycidae.org, www.lamiinae.org,
www.biolib.cz

Distribution: Philippines (Luzon Island).

Type: DUBC

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